

The Great Ant Scooter Group

EXT Drizzly night. Bus stop. Boy throws broken iPhone in a basket of cheesy nachos. Winston and Ben find it. Winston studies the ants on it.

Ben sees that the ants have little objects next to them, scooters.

WINSTON

Hey they look like tiny aliens.
(Gets out magnifying glass).

BEN

Ants and aliens both have antennae.

WINSTON

Look they have tiny scooters!

BEN

Let me see. You're right.

WINSTON

Do you think they can talk?

BEN

Let's find out.

WINSTON

What are you doing with scooters?

WORKER ANT

We ride them around the garden.

HEAD ANT

We want you to take care of us!

BEN

Don't worry – we're going to show you to WINSTON'S mom.
She studies guys like you.

WINSTON and BEN find intelligent talking ants

WORKER ANT

We're not stupid. We know a lot about your civilization.

WINSTON: I'm going to take them home. You don't mind do you BEN?

BEN

You found them WINSTON. They need to be protected.

WINSTON

My mom doesn't like bugs in the house. But they will be OK for one night.

BEN

In that case I had better take them home. My mom is an entomologist by the way.

WINSTON

What's that? Entomologist?

BEN

She studies insects.

EXT. Night. The boys get on the back of the bus with the ants.

INT. Night. Ben brings the ants home to his mom. In Ben's room.

WINSTON (to his mom)

We found these amazing ants with scooters and found they're capable of intelligent conversation.

MOM

What! That would be the greatest thing for me. Open the container, please.

WORKER ANT

They promised to take care of us.

MOM

How much do you know?

HEAD ANT

Lots. We're waiting for the Messiah Ant to come back from the cadre of expert ant scientists.

MOM

What do the ant scientists know?

WORKER ANT

They know how to keep us alive forever. We don't know yet, but we're sure.

MOM

Amazing. WINSTON, I'll talk more to them after dinner.

BEN

Now the ants are trying to make a sign silently.

MOM

Tiny scooters.

BEN

Look at the patterns they are forming. It's some kind of dance.

MOM

I've never seen anything like this before.

BEN

They are spelling out a word in Morse Code with their bodies in patterns.

.-

-.
-

...

MOM
It spells ants!

BEN
I can see their mouths moving.

MOM
I am going to write a paper.

BEN
You'll be famous!

MOM
Or colleagues will think I'm crazy.

MOM
I want to tape some interviews with you two ants
and publish them in the scientific literature.

BOTH ANTS
Agreed, and we're confident that you'll keep us safe for our Great Day. We're
letting you know a big secret. There are all sorts of insect species that converse
in different human languages and we'll put you in contact with them. It will
be a new era. We will share our knowledge with human beings.

MOM
Fine. I'll be instantly famous.

BEN
You'll be instantly famous like Claude Shannon for his
A MATHEMATICAL THEORY OF COMMUNICATION.

Scene The morning after Ben's mom is up late doing the paper for
ENTOMOLOGY TODAY.

BEN
Mom, here's the URL for the Youtube video:
talkingants.xyzi23zztop3

MOM

Thanks. It's easy to put it in WORD. I was up to 3AM doing the manuscript. Do we have time for a supplementary video?

BEN

Yeah I got up early and set it up in my room. Come on!

MOM

Great. (Talks to HEAD ANT) Tell me more!

HEAD ANT: We know there's going to be an AirChipShip race to celebrate the advent of interspecies communication.

MOM

How do you know that?

WORKER ANT

We have a PROPHET ANT! The PROPHET ANT is going to speak to you now.

PROPHET ANT

We are hoping for the death of the internal combustion engine and that humanity stop using fossil fuels that endanger the planet.

MOM

Amazing. BEN are you getting this?

BEN

For certain, MOM.

MOM

What can the various species offer us?

PROPHET ANT

We have scientists of our own and have carefully engineered this revealing. We want you to waste no time getting this on the ENTOMOLOGY TODAY website and have links to further videos.

WORKER ANT

The PROPHET ANT has to be kept far from the HEAD ANT because they are both deity. We all share eternal life with the Blessed Virgin.

MOM

OK BEN, that's enough.

MUSIC INTERLUDE WHOLE NEW YOU SHAWN COLVIN

BEN

MOM, here's the second URL: talkingants2.xyz456zztop4.com

BEN'S MOM RUSHES TO THE DEN TO UPLOAD THE NEW MANUSCRIPT

- screen fades to bright rainbow -

MOM

They'll think I'm crazy. I'll be sent to a mental institution and be put away and my colleagues will laugh at me.

BEN

They won't mom, the videos will convince 'em and show them ants are smart and we'll have interspecies communication.

MOM

This is the big break that'll put me on the map!

BEN

I have already discussed some things with the ants and they know a lot about human culture and science. They have science of their own and are concerned with the problem of everlasting life and lament that few humans care. The humans are interested in accumulating wealth and power and are irreligious.

MOM

Great job, BEN. We'll take videos and they can introduce us to the grasshoppers and others.

MR. NEILSEN AND THE SCIENCE CLUB WILL MEET THE ANTS
TOMORROW

Granny's alarm goes off.

GRANNY: Heavens tobbagans! Is it football? Ah, the eclipse!!! Partial SOLAR Eclipse begins Oct 23 at 1:53 PM PST 199° South-SW 36° Eclipse as seen from earth The Moon touches the Sun's edge. Maximum Eclipse at 3:17 PM 222° SW 30.2° Moon is closest to Sun center Partial Eclipse ends at 4:33 PM 238° West-Southwest 18.7° The Moon leaves the Sun's edge. Enjoy safely.

BEN and WINSTON take the talking ants to their school.

After the class bell rings, the students are in class at the middle school.

BEN to SUSIE

At recess I've got a surprise!

SUSIE

OK I'll wait until recess.

TEACHER

And we see that the angles of a triangle add up to 180 degrees. Now for the next topic.

MUSIC INTERLUDE COLDPLAY THE SCIENTIST

Scene changes to the playground.

SUSIE

OK BEN what's the surprise?

BEN

WINSTON had 'em, they're talking ants with little scooters.

SUSIE

Let me see WINSTON.

WINSTON shows SUSIE the ants and they start talking to SUSIE.

HEAD ANT

We're waiting for our Messiah ant.

SUSIE

You mean like Jesus? I wear a cross.

HEAD ANT

We know about the Cross and we have a Messiah of our own but we have no sin.

SUSIE

I thought it affected everything!

CO-ANT

Not so. It only affects humans but we need to be saved from entropy, which is the curse of ADAM.

SUSIE

Well, I pray to Jesus to solve my problem. How are you going to solve your problem?

BEN

My MOM is going to become famous after we took videos of the ants and she publishes, but we are an atheist household.

WINSTON

See they have scooters to get them around.

SUSIE

How are you ants going to solve your problem?

HEAD ANT

We're waiting for the ANT MESSIAH to get back from the SUCCESSION OF CREATORS and they will have the science solution.

SUSIE

When is that?

CO-ANT

It is on a schedule. It is not like the Second Coming which is unknown.
We are not subject to sin.

SUSIE

That is good but I wear a crucifix.

HERE COMES THE SUN The Beatles

Recess bell rings and they go to their next class.

- screen fades to green -

INT. Parker High School – Morning

DR NEILSEN

Maybe you should get more sleep at home Tommy. I'm trying to teach
you Chemistry.

EXTRA

We don't need to know Chemistry DR NEILSEN.

EXTRA

Science is for losers.

EXTRA

DR NEILSEN I just go to high school to socialize with my friends and
wear cool clothes.

EXTRA

You're overqualified to teach us.

EXTRA

All I care about is the Senior Prom.

TOMMY

I don't want to learn. I want to sleep.

=====

EXT. camera fades to high school plaza where dorky ‘cool’ cheerleaders are practicing and the one on top falls.

=====

INT. Day. Middle schoolers meet at DR NEILSEN’S clubhouse/workshop and bring the ants. They do a Chemistry experiment.

=====

INT. April and Doris take the iPhone to the mall to salvage the electronic components including the camera.

KIOSK REPAIR PERSONNEL
How can I help you?

APRIL
We need to keep the camera.

KIOSK REPAIR PERSONNEL
What are you doing with the camera?

DORIS
Saving it for a project.

APRIL
It’s for a robotics competition, part of our science club.

KIOSK REPAIR PERSONNEL
Cool. Good luck winning that.

April’s teenage sister is leaving a teenager boutique with some goth accessories. She has trouble backing out in the parking lot. A recycling truck goes by.

Advertisement on insect Internet: set in the glen near BEN’S household

Banner reading ALL INSECTS TO MEET AT THE TULIP PATCH 2:00PM appears

VOICEOVER
In the glen, the insects have their own society away from it all.

QUICKLY THEY GATHER, 50,000 strong 159 species, with the talking ants leading

ANT QUEEN

We have gathered here in need of guidance from the creators.

BEE QUEEN

I was doused in Royal Jelly so that I could be here.

GRASSHOPPERS

We saw the ad on the insect Internet and we expect something!

Other species watch the leaders

All of the insects enter into deep, deep prayer after they are all gathered.

Suddenly, there is a voice from the cloud, "The talking ants have communed with humans for the first time and interspecies communication has begun." It is not like the Tower of Babel that fell with a crash. It is truly the end.

The VOICEOVER continues, "The ant creators got eternal life from the ant scientists in advance of the Second Coming of Jesus."

HEAD GRASSHOPPER

What will become of the other species?

ANT QUEEN

This is being worked out by the ant scientists.

BEE QUEEN

Pope Francis, the world's #1 Catholic, has realized the problem is at Church and is tricky. Timing is the issue. Only God the Father Almighty has the knowledge and power to bring in the Kingdom.

There is a general consensus among the species that the meeting is over, so they dissipate, very hopeful.

- screen goes to bright white -

INT. DR NEILSEN'S clubhouse. RAJ visits and meets the middle schoolers with ANABEL and BRENT, ants.

RAJ brings a micro microphone so the ants can be heard. Ants introduce themselves. RAJ is amazed.

ANABEL

We are in the electronics club at our high school and we really want to learn. In our world now everyone is obsessed with jobs such as accountants, informants, agents, FBI agents.

BRENT

We can learn from humans and they can learn from us!

ANABEL

Remember, the PROPHET ANT said there's going to be an AirChipShip race in Atlanta at Georgia Tech.

BRENT

And the species are going to pilot the ships in honor of BEN'S MOM'S award-winning manuscript on interspecies communication.

ANABEL

I think we're going to go on a journey, but we will make it back to Atlanta!

BRENT

In the meantime, we'll learn about electronics with the middle schoolers.

Scene during work on AirChipShip at Paragon Labs. DR PHLOGISTON and DR TURMERIC oversee, and there are various technicians of varying levels of expertise.

DR TURMERIC

Well, we've been at it a month now and it was easy to decide the AirChipShips should be tiny helicopters with Dorito blades for the main rotor and tail rotor.

TECHNICIAN 1

According to thermodynamics, the micromotors need to be cooled down by miniature fans. Because there is a problem with evaporation, we found the Clausius-Clapeyron equation applies

$$\ln P_2/P_1 = \Delta H/R(1/T_1-1/T_2)$$

and we used it to predict the size of the fan, the speed and how to position it with flow equations.

TECHNICIAN 2

Yes, but we think there is a problem from a dimensional analysis standpoint and we haven't figured it out. The heat from the engine results in evaporation as you said but the helicopter is unbalanced.

DR TURMERIC

That is wrong. It is not dimensional analysis. You have to think about the center of gravity of a solid object. (thinks)

TECHNICIAN 3

Joke time! In prison block C of the Mississippi State Penitentiary after the 8PM lock down on Tuesday night an inmate yells, 45! Uproarious laughter ensues. New guy looks questioningly at his cellmate. Cellmate: That's the numbered joke from the joke book in the prison library. So the guy goes down next day and finds a good joke. Wednesday night after lock down he yells: 50! Dead silence. Looks at cellmate. Cellmate: You're not telling it right!

DR TURMERIC

What if the lifers run out of jokes?

TECHNICIAN 2

Obviously the motor for the main rotor has to be independent from the one for the tail, so what gives?

DR TURMERIC

Think about the shape of the fuselage. We can put everything into the computer and make the center of gravity come where it should. The fuselage should be longer and thinner. The computer can easily model it from helicopter engineering. We know where the center of gravity should be for it to fly.

TECHNICIAN 1

I remember that from my aerodynamics class.

DR PHLOGISTON

OK, that solves all of it. Just for fun, let's have Dr. Turmeric tell us about the rotor tilt problem.

DR TURMERIC

That involved some creative math and I have a proposed manuscript for publication. In tensor analysis of helicopter flight, I was the only one who got it right. Turns out it is the following formula and I had to add φ_i for the Dorito blade tilt. This is it for the tensor matrix elements, $k = 1,2,3$ for the three blades.

$\psi_k = \psi_1 + (k-1)2\pi/n_b + \varphi_i$ where $\varphi_{1,2,3} = 8.7^\circ$ for the main Dorito rotors and $\varphi_4 = 7.9^\circ$ for the tail Dorito rotor.

TECHNICIAN 2

I bet it gets published!

WE R IN CONTROL Neil Young

Camera pans around the lab, stops on the Miller equation

$$\Delta T = 3kT_2wMW_1 / \sigma aMW_2$$

DR TURMERIC

We're trying to do something with the Miller equation.

- scene fades to black -

Paragon labs, two administrators and a secretary discuss the AirChipShip + Erik Miller's Eq. (19)

administrator 1 = Robert Wolf

administrator 2 = Ted Cruz

secretary = Suzy Smart

Scene in an office in Paragon Labs: Robert Wolf and Ted Cruz are Assistant Research VPs and Suzy Smart is secretary for Ted Cruz.

ROBERT

We have to discuss some projects in the labs, but we have limited time.

TED

What's on the list, SUZY?

SUZY

Well, the AirChipShip development needs attention.

ROBERT

Oh, yes! DR PHLOGISTON and DR TURMERIC and their technicians are on it.

TED

We know they are very competent, so what's the concern?

SUZY

They need additional funding for the Great Insect Race celebrating communication between the species.

ROBERT

I've heard that the insects have different species to pilot the ships. In other words, the ships are not identical.

SUZY

It's well within budget, so it is doable.

TED

ROBERT and I have the authority and we agree, so it's done. What about ERIK MILLER'S Eq. (19)?

SUZY

No one knows, but both of you know about Chemical Engineering.

ROBERT

It has gone unnoticed except for computer people.

TED

Why don't we figure out how to publicize it? Obviously, Miller has correct data that agrees exactly with theory.

SUZY

That can be the only solution. We'll end the meeting now.

- fades to red -

INT. Dilapidated ant apartment in the wall of a brick apartment building.
Ant police knock at door. Derelict ant looks through peephole and
stashes crumbs behind the couch.

COPS

Open up its the police.

DERELICT ANT

Do you have a warrant?

ANT COP 1

No we don't happen to have them.

ANT COP 2

Oh shucks. The judges don't work on the weekend.

ANT DERELICT

We'll come back and get one. (slams door)

ANT DERELICT

(opens door again) OK Hey I think there's a beauty pageant we could be
watching instead (ant in a white tank top).

ANT COP 2

Good point. We could be watching that.

ANT COP 1

Sir have you been drinking tonight?

ANT DERELICT

No. Honest officers. I gave that up. Been sober now 15 months.

ANT COPS

Good for you.

ANT COP 1

Good but next time be more respectful.

DERELICT ANT

Or else what?

COP 1

We'll have that warrant and investigate your crumb crimes.

ANT DERELICT

Please go away now.

ANT COP 2

Hey we could arrest you for that.

ANT DERELICT

You're making me a little nervous. I apologize.

ANT COP 2

Yeah alright.

ANT COP 1

Sorry to bother you sir.

ANT COP 2

Have a good evening.

=====

Dialogue in Dr. Gaines lab with Erik Miller and the radio is on with mood music in the background.

DR GAINES

Hand me the crescent wrench.

ERIK MILLER

There's a bulletin on the radio!

THEY BOTH INTENTLY LISTEN

RADIO

We have interrupted the program with news from Tehran brought by CNN.

ANNOUNCER

Mahmoud Ahmadinejad, the former dictator of Iran, has been seized by paramilitary police at his house for two murders on Iran citizens! The evidence was given by his cronies for \$50 million U.S. dollars apiece and they are exonerated by Rohani for their crimes for turning state's evidence. Top secret couriers were used to take testimony to Rohani that was put together to get him on the murders. As soon as the evidence agreed, Ahmadinejad was arrested and put in a soundproof cell, where he awaits trial. Under Iranian law, a former leader cannot be executed, so he will live in solitary indefinitely. He is now believed to be the beast in DANIEL and REVELATION, but the devil is damned by action of the Virgin Mary. There is consensus that Israel will shortly rule the planet due to the immediacy of the coming of the Messiah. Israel is crying out and it will be life from the dead. There will be more details later.

MUSIC INTERLUDE NEIL YOUNG CRIME IN THE CITY

GAINES

Thanks for the wrench.

MILLER

About time that guy got his! I went on a trip to Israel in high school and liked it.

GAINES

I don't think we should mess with the AirChipShip race.

MILLER'S

You're right. The pilots need to be the insect species.

- screen fades to black -

INT. Evening. Ant Beauty Pageant

They watch beauty pageants.

The contestants wear zip codes on their sashes.

Notice on outside door reads:
This man, former President of
Iran, is here for slaying and
dooming many: Mahmoud Ahmadijad.

The Antichrist in the sound-proof room

INT. Day. Fighting backstage at the ant beauty pageant over dresses and bins of shoes.

MANAGER

You all look the same. This is ridiculous.

ANT PAGEANT CONTESTANT 1

No we do not look the same. I take offense at that.

ANT PAGEANT CONTESTANT 2

I'm going to win this beauty pageant and I need the right dress.

ANT PAGEANT CONTESTANT 3

Excuse me. You are not going to win because I am going to win.

MANAGER

Ladies calm down, you all look amazing. There are plenty of lovely evening gowns to go around.

ANT PAGEANT CONTESTANT 3

I found that dress first. It's mine. Give it back.

ANT PAGEANT CONTESTANT 4

I can't find my deodorant!

INT. Day. ANT BEAUTY PAGEANT

JUDGE 1

What talents do you have for the judges, contestant 35435?

CONTESTANT 35435

I can *rant* about what's fundamentally wrong with the national obsession with ant beauty pageants. They don't appreciate inner beauty.

JUDGE 2

No please don't do that.

JUDGE 3

We don't want to hear that.

CONTESTANT 35435

I can walk up walls.

JUDGE 1

We can all do that you don't have to.

Curtain goes up. Contestant is waiting for music to start for clog dancing.

JUDGE 2

Just wait for the evening gown competition, OK?

CONTESTANT 94704 blows them away with her clog dancing, a really great rendition from the Dutch.

JUDGE 1

94704 wins the clog dancing.

HOST

On to the evening gown competition.

Curtain goes down, then up for scenery change.

The contestants are all modeling their evening gowns. They take turns to see the front and their backs.

JUDGE 1

35435 wins the evening gown competition.

JUDGE 2

Now on to the part where the contestants answer a question.

JUDGE 3

35435, what are you hoping for?

CONTESTANT 35435

I'm hoping for the day when we all get along, when there is truly world peace.

JUDGE 2

94704, what are you hoping for?

CONTESTANT 94704

I am hoping for the day when even the poor get enough to eat and it will not be a crime to eat.

JUDGES 1,2,3

We are unanimous – 35435 wins the question session.

JUDGE 2

Now we are down to two contestants. The contest is between 94704 and 35435.

JUDGE 3

Now the moment you've been waiting for. Is the audience ready for the swimsuit competition?

JUDGE 1

This means 35435 wins because she has the most stunning ant body.

JUDGE 3

Congratulations 35435 you are the winner.

JUDGE 2

There she goes, as beautiful as ever.

Contestant 35435 is wearing the tiara walking down the stage and waving at the crowd.

They flee from the omnipresent and omnipotent police's crumb crime unit, seeing the look on Frida's face at the intersection crosswalk. They knew they would be falsely accused of a crumb crime. (The only crimes in the ant world are crumb crimes, that is, stealing of crumbs.) There is a room with dozens of sleuths working around the clock on swivel chairs, some checking Ant Facebook while on the job.

NUTRITION 202 at Georgia Institute of Technology

STEVE

I'm Steve Bishop, your professor for Nutrition 202, a graduate class for the Master's

candidates. I'm going to talk about Jennings' result in PAKISTAN JOURNAL OF NUTRITION, March 2012.

BOB GELDORF (student)

What relevance does Jennings' result have?

STEVE

Important for certain kinds of diet doctors who recommend serious calorie reduction or total fasting for weight reduction. But, on with his result. Jennings did a pilot study, the first of its kind on a sample size of N=51 male and female diets.

MARY DAY (student)

Has this result been tested in human trials?

STEVE

I know of one diet doctor who is putting together a study in Pennsylvania with his patients and hopes to publish soon. Preliminary findings indicate that the constant Jennings got is correct.

BOB GELDORF

I've seen the paper in the reading material for the course and it is almost exclusively arithmetic.

STEVE

Here it is (writes on chalkboard).

$$D = 3511 \text{ cal/lb @ } 52\% \text{ fasting rate for men and women}$$

MARY DAY

Kind of makes sense because human metabolism is the same for all normal men, proved in Jennings' IJRRAS November 2012 paper, also in the course reading material.

STEVE

Moreover, these results show that, for weight loss, the value is 3500 cal/lb across the entire fasting range. Now, we have to break for the lab/computer part of Nutrition 202.

- screen fades to orange -

GRANNY

The funniest thing happened today in the kitchen. Crumbs from my homemade chocolate cookies were missing off the plate.

FRIDA

Did you see the sugar ants responsible?

GRANNY

No. I was in the other room when it happened.

FRIDA

You should report these criminals. I have the number for the crumb crimes unit. They will investigate and bring the criminals to justice.

EXT. Night. Granny goes to Church. Granny only goes to Church because she met Frida there. Frida wears glasses and a lavender sweater.

=====

INT. Granny went to Church to tell Frida that when she went into the kitchen the crumbs were missing and she didn't see it happen.

Granny and Frida are at the Church potluck at St. Bonaventure Church on Tuesday evening.

GRANNY

What a nice potluck. I see our dishes are popular.

FRIDA

Lots of people came tonight.

GRANNY

You know those ants must have been stealing crumbs, but BEN'S MOM found out they are intelligent ants.

FRIDA

What?

GRANNY

His mom became instantly famous for her new ENTOMOLOGY TODAY article on interspecies communication. It went viral! Georgia Institute of Technology is putting on an AirChipShip race because of the paper

on the revelation. Ben's mom got an immediate offer of Professor of Entomology at Boston University.

FRIDA

I especially like this casserole. I'll have seconds.

GRANNY

I'm going to go easy on the famous ants for stealing crumbs. There's 144,000 of them in the gardens and the glen.

FRIDA

What do they do?

GRANNY

The ants are industrious and have ant scientists, their religion and little scooters.

FRIDA

Do they know about Jesus?

GRANNY

Yes, they know about Jesus! They have a message from their PROPHET ANT.

FRIDA

Well, I'm going for seconds.

- screen fades to brown -

INT. Early evening. Police transcript/call record.

GRANNY (picks up phone)

Hello this is the police.

ANT DISPATCHER

State your emergency.

GRANNY

I had reported an ant crumb crime, but now I'm retracting the allegation.

ANT DISPATCHER

Very well, Ma'am, we'll strike it from the record.

Georgia Tech Physics Laboratory

DR JONES

Lordy! We've perfected the first large-scale room temperature quantum computer ahead of the MIT group! Congratulations, everybody.

DR SMITH

It's incredible what we have. It has implications in detecting and preventing earthquakes, creating weather, and also probing into the human brain to repair and create new tissue!

DR JONES

Go into some detail.

DR SMITH

OK It involves high power X-Ray lasers to get down into seismic faults and relieve stress. We figured out a way to connect the quantum computer to most lasers and selectively influence events underground. The equation for earthquakes is:

$$R = \log [I / I(0)]$$

where R is the Richter level and I(0) is the reference level. The object is to lower I, thus lowering the magnitude of the quake. Our system, in initial trials, has already been tested out on the San Andreas fault. The quantum computer is very sensitive to detect feedback from stress in the rock and even more a very powerful X-Ray laser eased the stress by bringing down I, the applied stress.

DR JONES

What about the other applications?

DR SMITH

There are military people coming in here.

DR JONES

Well you know, we get funding and structure directly from the Joint Chiefs of Staff.

ARMY COLONEL

We're taking all this for exclusive military use along with your two top people and you will have different things to do in this lab.

ARMY LIEUTENANT

We can't imagine what we'll do with this: surveillance, codes and communication.

ARMY COLONEL

True, now let us take over.

The work at the lab becomes classified.

- screen fades to purple -

EXT. Afternoon. The ants turn the corner and see their opportunity to escape because of their crumb crimes, because they committed crumb crimes against others than GRANNY. A Florida orange truck is parked across the street. They take a journey across America in the orange truck and wind up stranded in the desert of Arizona. They also see a UFO in Roswell NM. Then it is on to a honky tonk saloon in Texas and a truck stop in El Paso.

Ant&nt is the phone company the ants use to place a collect call to their mom. Their mom accepts the call but gets mad because it is expensive. They ask their mom to put on their auntie who will understand.

Auntie tells them how to find coyote.

MOM

Are you really in trouble?

ANTS

No. Were far from home and want to talk to AUNTIE.

AUNTIE

Hello. I'll help you get back to Atlanta.

INSANE IN THE MEMBRANE Cypress Hill

Technology with Gaines/Miller at Georgia Technology

GAINES

GENERAL RUTHERFORD, I have technology that may be of use to you.

RUTHERFORD

Oh, something new? Thought I'd heard the latest.

GAINES

I have a really good student ERIK MILLER who solved the problem of bubble nucleation in polymer solutions at University of Kentucky for his Master's before he came here.

RUTHERFORD

Tell me about that.

GAINES

People first started to make a dent in the problem in 1985, but only ERIK fully solved it in 2014.

RUTHERFORD

Show me the equation.

GAINES

ERIK, come over here!

MILLER

Sir, here it is on the chalkboard, My equation (19).

Looks nice, eh?

$$\Delta T = 3kT^2 \frac{WMW_1}{\sigma a MW_2}$$

RUTHERFORD

What is it good for?

$$\frac{d \ln A}{dK} = \frac{1}{6K}$$
$$\Delta T = \frac{3kT^2 \Delta W_1}{6a \Delta W_2}$$

Erik is pointing to equation 19, and he got data that agreed exactly with theory doing his M.S. at good ol' U of K in 2014.

Before Erik Miller came to Dr. Gaines lab, he solved the problem of limit of super heat of polymer solutions at University of Kentucky.

Erik Miller in Gaines lab; Eq. (19)

MILLER

I've done some more research on it and know it is mathematically exact, but have been wondering what its purpose is.

RUTHERFORD (to GAINES)

So what is new?

GAINES

We work on engineering here at GIT and ERIK studied Mechanical Engineering and Chemistry before he came here. We are interested in the way things fly.

RUTHERFORD

That interests me greatly.

MILLER

I've done some new calculations on the angle tilt of helicopters and the position of the center of gravity. We both think they're correct.

RUTHERFORD

This has to be classified, so the NSA contractor stepped in and said this is not to be published but only shared with the military.

GAINES

But we publish and what about ERIK'S doctorate?

RUTHERFORD

MILLER can get his doctorate, don't worry. Congratulations on your equation and establishing that it is exact.

GAINES

This is so sudden.

RUTHERFORD

The President is aware of this. We cannot have World War III.

MILLER

What does this have to do with world war?

RUTHERFORD

It has to do with Israel's attitude toward Iran.

GAINES

That's heavy.

- screen fades to black -

EXT. GRANNY is in the backyard watering the roses. She likes to watch them bloom and gets out of bed by the alarm clock. She observes a bumble bee taking a shower in a flower bed while using the garden hose.

MUSIC VIVALDI SPRING

GRANNY

Heavens Tobbagans. Is it Superbowl Sunday? Don't tell me I missed the eclipse.

A termite is chewing the porch on GRANNY'S house and proposes to an aphid eating a tulip petal. A beetle and caterpillar are watching.

TERMITE

Pardon me ma'am but do you believe in love at first sight?

APHID

I'm trying to eat this leaf for breakfast. Do you mind?

TERMITE

Can I get your number? I don't mean to be so forward but I'd like to give you a call sometime.

APHID

You're not exactly my type. You're too rugged. I go for the more cerebral.

TERMITE

I say we go on a date sometime.

CATERPILLAR

Did you hear that? The termite is in love with the aphid.

LADYBUG

They make a beautiful couple. Don't they Henry?

Georgia Tech Flying Robotics Competition

GRANNY holds up a giant Fresnel lens and it makes the ants appear to be as large as hot dogs.

Dramatic scene: AirChipShip flying around the room. FRIDA watches. GRANNY holds up the Fresnel lens and it shows the ants glaring at ERIK MILLER and PROFESSOR GAINES.

Turbulence on the AirChipShip like on STAR TREK.

BRENT and ANABEL are hopping a ride across the Southwest in an orange truck.

ANABEL
How long until we get there?

BRENT
Do you see a payphone? We have to call AUNTIE.

ANABEL
Why?

BRENT
Auntie was a scout, she is very clever.

BRENT'S MOM (on the phone)
This long distance phone is costing too much!

AUNTIE
OK I'll talk to you. BRENT, how are you?

BRENT
Hi AUNTIE. COYOTE is going to help us.

In the morning the truck winds up in AZ.
The ants depart from the truck with their scooters and BRENT evades a tumbleweed charging at him by crouching low.

We are 99 miles from nowhere, so we gotta find Coyote.

DWIGHT YOAKUM 1000 Miles from Nowhere plays as the truck rolls into the small town.

EXT. Early dawn. By dawn BRENT, TONY and ANABEL have found the home of COYOTE. COYOTE is a high tech computer gamer and lives in a nice pad, an Anasazi cliff dwelling among the pinyons. It is only a few hours from where they were, so DANNY the June Bug offers them a ride on his dune buggy.

In the morning they glue their scooters to COYOTE'S fur with cactus sap.

An ant biker group appears on COYOTE'S left side and revs up. BORN TO BE WILD by Steppenwolf blares as the ant bikers approach.

ANT BIKER 1
Hey, whatcha doing up there on that coyote?

ANT BIKER 2 (husky voice)
Hey you want to go to Sturgis with us?

TONY
The life of a roadie. I will go to Sturgis someday.

ANT BIKER 3
Right on buddy.

ANT BIKER 2
Take it easy man!

(Ant bikers zoom off)

BRENT
That was interesting, an ant biker group.

EXT. Day. Dust storm flares up.

They have to take cover in an old mining shack.

The dust storm ends and COYOTE keeps walking.

OZZY and FRANCES, quirky retiree pincher bugs in a Winnebago show up at a gas station in a desert town.

COYOTE

Blisters mi amigos. (Pause)

This is about as far as I can take you.

COYOTE

The train will take you all the way to Chattanooga. That's not far from Marietta.

ANABEL

It the adventure of a lifetime. Like what teens like us did in the Great Depression.

COYOTE

Would you mind taking my friends here to the train depot?

It is 5 miles north.

OZZY

Of course, anything to help.

FRANCES

We would love to. Hop in.

COYOTE

You'd better get moving. The Chattanooga train should be arriving soon.

ALL

Thank you COYOTE.

COYOTE

Have a safe journey and be careful.

ANABEL, TONY, BRENT sit at the settee while FRANCES serves O.J. and mac & cheese. Willie Nelson's ON THE ROAD AGAIN plays.
(There is a rainbow sticker on the back window.)

The ants ride the rails to Chattanooga, TN.

ANABEL
Glad we got a ride from COYOTE and OZZY helped.

TONY
Right-O. It's going to be a long smooth ride so let's play a game.
20 questions, anyone?

BRENT
No. I've got a better idea. Let's talk about the scenery as we pass it in this boxcar. What was that that just went by?

ANABEL
I think it was a bird.

They all descend on a partially eaten lunch in a lunch box.

ANABEL
Hey! I think we have to change trains?

BRENT
No. OZZY heard the train operator and told me this train runs straight through to Chattanooga.

So they're set to make it to the scheduled AirChipShip race.

A HORSE WITH NO NAME by America

- screen fades to red -

One way or other they all make it to the race in time.

This next scene took place 2 days before the insect race.

Paragon Engineering Laboratory
DR PHLOGISTON DR TURMERIC
(Dorito blades, technicians)
MICROMOTOR

DR PHLOGISTON and DR TURMERIC are in charge of the Paragon lab where the AirChipShips are almost ready for the great race in two days. They are in conference.

DR PHLOGISTON
We have had good technicians at work for months.

DR TURMERIC
Yes. We're only concerned about the finishing touches now.

DR P
What's the latest?

DR T
There is a slight problem with the battery that runs the MICROMOTOR.

DR P
Any other problems?

DR T
Largely cosmetic, like how to paint the AirChipShips and the interior of the cockpit.

DR P
Don't forget – every ship has to have insect pilots.

DR T
This is excellent.

DR P
23 different species of insect are entered, in pairs, and the ants are seeded 2nd.

DR T

What was the best thing in this effort?

DR P

When my smartest technician had the idea of making the batteries run in parallel.

Technician rushes in: We solved the battery problem and the ships are ready for the race.

- screen fades to green -

Back at Georgia Tech

GAINES

OK, class. ERIK MILLER and I am sorry because the solution manual was lost and we couldn't find it. However, we want to collect the problem sets now and we have to buy another one. ERIK is going to talk now.

ERIK MILLER

I'd like to talk about my equation today.

$$\Delta T = 3kT^2 \frac{WMW_1}{\sigma a MW_2} \quad \text{Eq. (19)}$$

Here is the story behind Eq. (19). I was fighting this hairy-headed monster and it was a do-or-die situation. What if you were stranded somewhere in life and the education you got at GIT was intended to pull you through? That is what it was for me. I was holed up in this small studio apartment doing my University of Kentucky Master's and I had to calculate myself out of a hole. Anyway, I successfully derived Eq. (19) and proved it with a clever vector calculus argument, which was my contribution. I'm not sure it is a unique method. It shows the value of a good quality education because solving it was in some way like doing the physical chemistry problem sets.

GAINES

Thank you, ERIK.

GAINES and MILLER go to the faculty lounge and there's a woman physics professor drinking coffee. They both say Hi and she responds: What are you teaching the kids these days?

GAINES

ERIK did some physical chemistry and he thinks it has something to do with world affairs.

WOMAN PROF.

Is this some kind of joke?

GAINES

ERIK is sure it is related to 9/11!!

WOMAN PROF.

I'm outta here!

MILLER

You're right – they don't want to hear anything new!

- screen fades to white -

The ants that went across the country race back to get to the flying robotics competition at Georgia Tech.

They go to DR NEILSEN'S house but DR NEILSEN wasn't there.

They go across the street to GRANNY and run into GRANNY and FRIDA and explain they have a flying robotics contest to go to on the Georgia Tech campus.

Professor Gaines had told judges to disqualify the race because he wanted the ships to be automatically controlled. However, Gaines was overruled. Gaines was arrested for attempted destruction of property and interference with the race, but it was thrown out of court as he was issued a stay-away order.

AMOS is the ant pilot and ANDY is the ant copilot.

AMOS

Well, we've got the race well in hand.

ANDY

I honestly don't know why we're seeded 2nd.

AMOS

They don't know the ability of our zero-point energy magnet motor.
Ours is state of the art.

ANDY

Yes, lighter and more powerful than the other species.

AMOS

We're just trying to be a credit to our species.

GASG robotics competition dialogue

The Great Race starts.

AMOS

We got a good start out of the gate.

ANDY

Remember – the grasshoppers are the ones to beat.

AMOS

Keep bugging me about the blade tilt. I need your expertise in helicopter technology.

ANDY

Right-O!

AMOS

Here goes nothing.

ANDY

Around the first turn, the grasshoppers are a bit in front of us!

AMOS

How about the blade tilt?

ANDY

I have the tilt adjusted to increase engine efficiency.

AMOS

I'm glad we have a zero-point energy magnet motor,
light and powerful!

- music interlude WE R IN CONTROL by Neil Young while the ant team
pulls up neck-in-neck with the leader, the grasshoppers, and then they
are in front before the last turn.

ANDY

Wow, wasn't that sure we would do it!

AMOS

We're doing it, we're going it!

Music ACROSS THE GREAT DIVIDE by Nanci Griffith

Ants win by a nose and are crowned champions.

- screen fades to green -

AT THE FINISH LINE

AMOS

I can't believe it! We actually won fair and square. Nobody is going to
rob us of this.

ANDY

No way. I was just talking to the grasshoppers and they congratulated us, but
there is some exceedingly good news. The scuttlebutt is that the Supreme Ant
got back from the Eternal Creators and they know that Jesus Christ is
going to solve the problem of entropy, which has been death.

AMOS

This is a new beginning for interspecies communication and the insect species
share in the life of all beings.

LAST
THUR
DAY

Ants overtake grasshoppers in Air-ship race

There are three papers in science which have to do with this screen play. Here they are, in chronological order, with brief annotations. They come from Jennings' research, one of the authors.

1. John H. Jennings and Michael Lesser, M.D. "Weight loss and calorie restriction at 50% fasting rate" PAKISTAN JOURNAL OF NUTRITION March 2012.

This paper builds on a previous paper and established that the calories per pound of body weight in humans is 3500 cal/lb across the entire fasting range.

2. John H. Jennings "Metabolism is universal" IJRRAS November 2012.

This paper derives a result based on calculus that agrees with a study in the early 1900s for the basal metabolic rate showing a formula applying only to men.

3. John H. Jennings "Homogeneous nucleation from polymer solutions" POLYMERS RESEARCH JOURNAL Vol. 8. No. 4 2014.

Using elementary algebra and simple calculus, one of the authors derived Eq. (19) in this screenplay.

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